

LEGAL ISSUES OF A MEDIATOR WHEN MEDIATION: THEORY AND PRACTICE

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of requirements for mediators, factors of trust in the mediator of participants in a disputed legal relationship. It is concluded that the mediator is a capable, independent and neutral person, voluntarily elected by the parties to assist them in resolving the conflict.

Key words: mediator, neutral person, independent person, conflict, elected person.

According to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 2018 No. ZRU-482 “On Mediation”, a mediator is a person engaged by the parties to conduct mediation. Today, there is no unity of understanding of the legal status of the mediator¹. Approximately the same way this issue is resolved in many conciliation regulations and provisions².

It follows from the texts of these documents that the mediator may be elected by the parties from the lists maintained by organizations engaged in activities related to reconciliation, and the parties may also elect as a mediator another person not included in these lists. This leads to the conclusion that the requirements for these candidates must be different³. If the parties have the right to choose a different person, therefore, this person may have a different education than the persons included in the lists, other work experience, etc.⁴.

When determining the candidacy of an intermediary, the main factor is the trust in this person of the participants in the disputed legal relationship. Obviously, it is necessary to fix in the law the general requirements for the candidacy of a mediator, which, in principle, will not limit the will of the parties, but will contribute to the selection of a more suitable candidate⁵.

¹ Аболонин В. Медиация и саморегулирование: точки соприкосновения // ЭЖ-Юрист. 2009. № 33. С. 8

² <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/4185961>

³ Садовникова, М. Н., & Анищенко, А. С. (2019). Требования, предъявляемые к медиатору: современные подходы и тенденции развития института. *Сибирский юридический вестник*, (4), 114-118.

⁴ Ibratova, F. (2021). Legal Problems of the Concepts Legality, Justification and Justice by Judicial Acts. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 16.

⁵ Усманова, Е. Ф. (2019). Зарубежный опыт работы в области семейной медиации и требования, предъявляемые к медиаторам. *Вопросы российского и международного права*, 9(9-1), 24-30.

It seems that two groups of criteria should be established to determine the candidacy of a mediator: 1) common for persons included in the lists of mediators and for other persons; 2) relating only to persons included in the lists of intermediaries.

It seems that the first group should include the following criteria:

- 1) legal capacity of a person;
- 2) no conflict of interest;
- 3) independence in relation to the parties.

It should be noted that according to Art. 21 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a citizen's legal capacity arises in full from the onset of adulthood, that is, upon reaching the age of eighteen. It is from this age that a person begins to understand the meaning of his actions, manage them and foresee their consequences, can independently conclude contracts, perform other legal actions and be responsible for them, which is very important when conducting a conciliation procedure.

It is now recognized that both representatives of a third party external to the conflict (“neutral outsiders”) and persons associated with any of the conflicting parties (“biased outsiders”) can act as intermediaries.⁶ Taking into account the obvious fact that the decisions of the mediator are not binding, are not secured by coercive force on the part of the state, the main thing to start from is the neutrality of the mediator⁷. If the mediator is associated with one of the parties to the dispute, the parties will initially be in an unequal position, which is likely to make it difficult to resolve the conflict⁸. However, there is a possibility that the other side will not be fully open during the conciliation process, and this will lead to a waste of time, and not to a settlement of the dispute.

Thus, a mediator is a capable, independent and neutral person, voluntarily chosen by the parties to assist them in resolving the conflict. (This definition is common both to persons included in the lists of intermediaries and to other persons.)

⁶ Барышова, М. В., Белый, В. С., Глушенко, В. М., Ибратова, Ф. Б., Новиков, А. Н., & Пронькин, Н. Н. (2019). Социальное предпринимательство: научные исследования и практика.

⁷ Разрешение конфликтов: пособие по обучению методам анализа и разрешения конфликтов. М., 1999. С. 4243. (цит. по: Альтернативное разрешение споров: учеб.-метод. комплекс / под ред. А.И. Зайцева. С. 329).

⁸ Ибратова Ф. Б. ПРАВОВЫЕ ПОСЛЕДСТВИЯ БАНКРОТСТВА ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЯ ИЛИ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ЛИЦА, УТРАТИВШЕГО СТАТУС ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЯ // Polish Journal of Science. – 2021. – №. 38-2. – С. 20-24.

It follows that any person who meets these requirements may be elected, by agreement of the parties, as a mediator to resolve their dispute⁹.

However, it seems that any such person will be of little use when choosing a mediator, and this will primarily be due to the difficulty of finding a person who is independent and neutral, but at the same time who is trusted by both parties and who is willing and prepared to play the role of mediator.

The experience of foreign countries confirms what has been said. Thus, according to a two-year evaluation conducted by independent experts with the assistance of the Ontario Attorney General's Office and the Civil Rights Committee, mediators are most frequently selected from the List; only 6% of intermediaries in Toronto were other persons, in Ottawa the choice of "off-list" intermediaries is even rarer.

Let us turn to the second category of persons - persons included in the lists of mediators of organizations that ensure the conduct of the conciliation procedure (hereinafter in the work they will be called "professional mediators (mediators)").

In order for a person to be included in the lists of intermediaries, it is not enough to meet the above criteria. Here, additional more stringent requirements should be established: the availability of the necessary education, work experience, etc.¹⁰.

For example, in accordance with the program of mandated mediation implemented in the courts of Toronto and Ottawa based on Rule 24.1, a legislative act entered into force on 01/04/1999 in the province of Ontario, the following criteria are guided by the following criteria for inclusion in the list of mediators:

- 1) the applicant's work experience as a mediator (at least five independent mediations are required), training in the mediation process, education received;
- 2) knowledge of the civil justice system;
- 3) recommendations¹¹.

In addition, according to an assessment conducted by independent experts with the assistance of the Ontario Attorney General's Office and the Civil Rights Committee, when interviewing individuals participating in mediation meetings, the majority of those interviewed felt that more stringent criteria should be

⁹ Ермаков, А. Н. (2020). К вопросу о расширении исключительных полномочий профессионального медиатора на нотариальную сферу. *Цивилистика: право и процесс*, (2), 58-63.

¹⁰ Ibratova F. B. The Concept and Characteristics of Bankruptcy Procedures for Business Entities With the Status of a Legal Entity // *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*. – 2022. – Т. 20. – С. 143-147.

¹¹ Галущина. И. Н. (2006). Понятия представительства и посредничества в гражданском праве: сравнительно-правовой аспект. *Журнал российского права*, (2 (110)), 139-147.

applied to select candidates for mediation to be included in List. They proposed to establish the following requirements for candidates: holding a certain number of mediations per year, and mandatory advanced training. In addition, the majority stated that it is mandatory to provide information about the biography, experience and area of specialization¹².

In order to be included in the Unified register of mediators in Bulgaria, it is necessary to submit “a certificate of qualification of a mediator, a document on the absence of a criminal record for crimes of a general nature and a declaration of liability in case of submission of false data”¹³.

Federal Law of Austria "On Mediation in Civil Matters" in sect. 3 establishes the following requirements for persons who have the right to be included in the List of intermediaries (mediators): reaching the age of full 28 years, obtaining special qualifications, are trustworthy, have entered into a liability insurance contract for causing harm¹⁴.

In the United States, there are no general mandatory requirements for an intermediary. However, in practice, preference is given to persons with certain experience and knowledge in a particular area of jurisprudence. In particular, retired judges, practicing judges and arbitrators, lawyers, persons who have completed a special training course and received a mediator certificate are involved as mediators.

At the same time, the legislation of individual states imposes minimum requirements for the qualification of an intermediary. For example, in Texas, the Alternative Dispute Resolution Act of 1987 requires a mediator to complete at least a 40-hour certified training program. Minnesota has a similar rule, but only for child custody dispute mediators¹⁵.

In other words, the main requirement for professional mediators should be the availability of professional education. But who should be the education mediator? Since he will have to participate in the settlement of legal disputes, apparently, he must be a lawyer, but not every lawyer can bring the parties to an agreement. To establish the true cause of the conflict and reconcile the parties, the mediator may need to be a good psychologist, but not every

¹²Гайдаенко-Шер, Н. И. (2017). Унификация требований к квалификации медиатора: медиатор и медиатор в семейных спорах. Актуальные проблемы российского права, (5 (78)), 56-60.

¹³Худойкина, Т. В., & Сайфетдинова, А. Ф. (2018). Требования, предъявляемые к медиаторам в России и за рубежом. Бюллетень науки и практики, 4(6), 324-327.

¹⁴Подольская Н., Михальченкова В. Новый Федеральный Закон Австрии «О посредничестве по гражданским делам» // Третейский суд. 2004. – № 4. – С. 37.

¹⁵Подольская Н., Михальченкова В. Новый Федеральный Закон Австрии «О посредничестве по гражданским делам» // Третейский суд. 2004. – № 4. – С. 37.

psychologist knows the rules of law and can help the parties reach a legal agreement.

This issue is also debatable in American literature. According to some researchers, in some cases an intermediary - a professional psychologist or psychotherapist will achieve more success than a lawyer. From the point of view of others, formal recognition of dispute mediation by the legal profession is of great practical importance, as it allows the formulation of clear qualification requirements that a mediator must meet; develop uniform standards of professional conduct and ethics; Finally, introduce intermediary professional liability insurance¹⁶.

Taking into account the experience of the United States, where retired judges, practicing judges and arbitrators, lawyers, i.e. persons with legal education and experience in legal practice, are involved as mediators, it seems that in Russia it is also necessary to move in this direction and to a greater extent part as intermediaries to use lawyers, especially in the arbitration process¹⁷. However, the mediation procedure can be applied in all areas of human life, and therefore, to resolve certain disputes, mediators with knowledge in the field of economics, accounting, etc. will be needed, under such circumstances, the mediator does not have to be a lawyer by profession, he may have other specialty.

Thus, it seems that a professional mediator can be a person who has a higher professional education and at least 2 years of work experience in a specialty that corresponds to the education received. At the same time, the parties are not limited in their choice and may involve a person with other characteristics as a mediator (for example, lack of work experience), but, as already mentioned, such an intermediary is a non-professional mediator.

And yet, the presence of only higher education and practice is not enough for the correct conduct of the mediation procedure. To be included in the list of professional mediators, a candidate must undergo special training.

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¹⁷ Григорьева, Н. В., & Ефремова, А. В. (2020). ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕБОВАНИЯ, ПРЕДЪЯВЛЯЕМЫЕ МЕДИАТОРУ. *Вестник студенческого научного общества ГОУ ВПО «Донецкий национальный*, 116.

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